

ANNOTATION: This article is about approaches and will give a definition for word formation, synchronic approaches, diachronic approaches, differences between synchronic and diachronic approaches and their similarities and provide some examples. In the 19th century, linguists concentrated on a language's historical features. Their primary focus was on analyzing various languages, how they have evolved over time, and classifying them into language families based on their shared ancestry. This entire field of study falls under diachronic linguistics.

KEY WORDS: Word formation, synchronic approach, diachronic approach, semantic relations.

Nowadays, the terms “word formation” does not have a clear cut, universally accepted usage. It is sometimes referred to all processes connected with changing the form of the word by, for example, affixation, which is a matter of morphology. In its wider sense word formation denotes the processes of creation of new lexical units. Although it seems that the difference between morphological change of a word and creation of a new term is quite easy to perceive, there is sometimes a dispute as to whether blending is still a morphological change or making a new word. There are, of course, numerous word formation processes that do not arouse any controversies and are very similar in the majority of languages.

Word formation is that branch of the science of language which the patterns on which a language forms new lexical units, i.e. words». (H.Marchand.) The term «word formation» is applied to the process by which new words are formed by adding prefixes and suffixes or both to a root — form already in existence. (J.A. Sheard).

Word formation is the creation of new words from the elements existing in the language. Every language has its own structural patterns of word formation. Words like «writer», «worker», «teacher», «manager» and many others follow the structural pattern of word formation «V + er». Word-formation may be studied synchronically and diachronically. «With regard to compounding, prefixing and suffixing word formation proceeds either on a native or on a foreign basis of coining. The term native basis of coining means that a derivative must be analysable as consisting of two independent morphemes (in the event of a compound as rainbow) or of a combination of independent and dependent morpheme (in the case of prefixal and suffixal derivatives as un-just, boy-hood).

Synchronic approach and its basic peculiarities.

The words childhood, kingdom were compound words: hood OE had (state, rank), dom OE dom condemn. But synchronically they are considered as derived words because «-dom,» «-hood» became affixes. The words «return» and «turn» historically had semantic relations and «return» was considered as a word derived from «turn». But synchronically these words have no semantic relations and we can't say that «return» is derived from «turn». A synchronic method, which derives from the Ancient Greek words for "together" and "time," looks at a language at a certain point in time without taking into consideration its history. The goal of

synchronic linguistics is to describe a language at a certain period, frequently the present. A diachronic (from "through" and "time") method, like that used in historical linguistics, takes into account how a language .

The study of Middle English is synchronic and focuses on comprehending how a certain period in English history operates as a whole when the topic is temporally restricted to a suitably homogeneous form. In contrast, the diachronic method compares the many stages to understand language evolution. The historical linguist Ferdinand de Saussure is frequently linked to the words "synchrony" and "diachrony," who saw the synchronic perspective as systematic but said that language development is too unpredictable to be deemed a system.as changed over time. Synchronic linguistics refers to the study of languages as they currently exist, without reference to their historical development. A nice illustration is the English word for "s" in the plural. In certain words, like "cats," this ending is really pronounced as a "s," whereas in others, like "dogs," it's pronounced as a "z." You may verify that this is accurate by saying the words aloud to yourself. The [s] ending appears after sounds like /t/, /k/, and /p/ that you pronounce without vibrating your voice box, according to an analysis of the words that have each ending. After vibrational ("voicing") sounds like /d/, /g/, /b/, and vowels comes the [z] ending. Since [s] lacks voice and [z] has voice, this makes perfect sense

The study of how components of a language (morphs or morphemes) come together to form words and phrases, as well as how good syntax gives a sentence meaning, is known as synchronic linguistics. A synchronous field of research in the 20th century is the quest for a universal grammar—that which is innate in people and enables them to learn their first language at an early age.

Diachronic approach and its main unique features.

A language's evolution across time is studied in diachronic linguistics. "Diachronic, which literally translates to "across time," refers to any work that charts the changes, divisions, and mutations of languages over time.

The "synchronic-diachronic" difference, which is still strong in twenty-first-century linguistics, was accepted by the majority of Saussure's successors. In practice, this means that it is considered a principle or linguistic method violation to include data pertaining to diachronically diverse states in the same synchronic analysis.

Diachronic linguistics refers to the study of how a language evolves over a period of time. Tracing the development of English from the Old English period to the twentieth century is a diachronic study. A synchronic study of language is a comparison of languages or dialects—various spoken differences of the same language—used within some defined spatial region and during the same period of time. Determining the regions of the United States in which people currently say 'pop' rather than 'soda' and 'idea' rather than 'idear' are examples of the types of inquiries pertinent to a synchronic study."

Language change is one of the subjects of historical linguistics, the subfield of linguistics that studies language in its historical aspects. Sometimes the term diachronic linguistics is used instead of historical linguistics, as a way of referring to the study of language (or languages) at various points in time and at various historical stages.

Differences between synchronic and diachronic approaches and their similarities

Diachronic linguistics is essentially the study of language across many historical eras. As a result, it investigates the historical development of language over time. Diachronic linguistics is the name of this subfield of linguistics. The following are the primary concerns of diachronic linguistics:

- describing and explaining apparent linguistic changes in certain languages;
- retracing the origins of languages, figuring out their relationships, and classifying them into language families

Creating broad hypotheses about language development and its causes;

Synchronic linguistics is the analytical study of a language at a specific moment, typically in its current form. It is also referred to as descriptive or general linguistics. However, studying a language at any period in the past also comes under this category; however, the study must solely focus on the state of the language at that time. It entails studying a language at a specific time without taking into account its developmental stages in the past or present.

In conclusion: additionally, a genuine diachronic work can only be created if the synchronic work is well-described. Although the term "synchronic method" has a misleading etymology—it meaning "with time"—it examines how a language is described, including its grammar, classification, and arrangement of components.

While diachronic linguistics, which literally translates as "across-time," examines the origins of words, compares languages, and charts how they have changed over time. The two strategies must be pursued separately because they are very dissimilar.

Time is the key distinction between diachronic and synchronic linguistics research. First off, prior to Saussure, all linguistic research was diachronic. The term "diachronic" rather accurately describes itself. Greek loanwords are prefixed with the dia- prefix, which denotes "through, between, across, by, of, or similar to." The Latin loanword *chronicus*, which was derived from the Greek *chronos*, which denotes time, gave rise to the root word *chronic* in English. The study of language across, through, or between periods of time is called diachronic linguistics.

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